

From Service to Skill: Livelihood of Śūdras in Vedic Society — A Socio-Economic Study

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Abstract: *The present study examines the livelihood of Śūdras in Vedic society within its broader socio-economic framework. Vedic literature reveals a diversified economy based on agriculture, pastoralism, crafts, trade, and ritual exchange, in which Śūdras played a vital productive role. Despite their lower position in the varṇa hierarchy, they were actively engaged in occupations such as domestic service, agriculture, animal husbandry, and especially artisanal activities like pottery, carpentry, weaving, and metalwork. Their labor formed the material foundation of the economy and supported the production and circulation of essential goods. Śūdras were also indirectly integrated into the ritual economy through their involvement in preparing sacrificial materials and through the redistribution of wealth via dakṣiṇā. The study concludes that the livelihood of Śūdras was characterized by both dependency and economic agency, highlighting their indispensable contribution to the sustainability and interdependence of the Vedic economic system.*

Keywords: *Vedic Economy, Wealth Concept, Livelihood, Śūdras, Cottage Industries.*

Introduction

The study of the ancient Indian economy finds its earliest expression in Vedic literature, which provides important insights into the structure of wealth and livelihood in early society. Texts such as the R̥gveda, Atharvaveda, and Brāhmaṇa literature reveal that wealth was not merely monetary but included cattle, food grains, natural resources, and productive labor. The Vedic economy was thus diversified, based on agriculture, pastoralism, crafts, and trade, and sustained through both material and ritual practices. Within this economic framework, the livelihood of the Śūdras occupies a significant position. Although placed at the lower end of the varṇa hierarchy, Śūdras were actively engaged in various forms of labor that supported the entire economic system. Their occupations included domestic service, agricultural work, animal husbandry, and a wide range of crafts such as pottery, carpentry, weaving, and metalwork. These activities formed the material base of the Vedic economy and ensured the production and circulation of essential goods.

Furthermore, the integration of economic life with ritual practices, particularly yajñas and the system of dakṣiṇā, indirectly involved Śūdras in the redistribution of wealth. Their role highlights the functional interdependence of different social groups, where economic sustainability depended on the contributions of all varṇas. Thus, this study seeks to examine the livelihood of Śūdras within the Vedic socio-economic system, emphasizing their productive role and essential contribution to the organization and continuity of early Indian economic life.

Kinds of economy in Vedic Society

The RV illustrate the natural sources of wealth- Fire, Air, Water, Earth and Sky etc. These immortal forces of Nature, dialectically self-disciplined, collectively create life - giving materials. They provide the daily renewable materials of food in abundance and other necessary things needed for the well-born (Sujata) of the primitive Indians in the land of Sarswati and the seven rivers. The Well-Born primitive Indians invest mere supervision and elementary care in form of their collective labour to transform the natural raw materials into the useful social wealth, means of their daily sustenance. So, these natural resources of living become Natural Social Wealth (NSW) socially managed. As we do not have any tangible record

of management, we can find the system of management only in the foteus form. Generally, it is assumed that goods which are demanded or desired, are called wealth. The possession of any of these- cattle, gold, progeny, corns etc. was recognized as wealth by the Vedic people. In Taittirīya Samhitā¹ cattle are clearly described as wealth. Similarly, sons and grandsons are mentioned as superior wealth². Corns are also characterized as wealth³.

In the vedas, we find twenty-four terms used for indicating different types of wealth. In explanation of these terms, we find the Vedic seers' concept of wealth. Vedic Aryans had a strong desire for the possession of wealth, food, cattle, and a long life for hundred years. In a mantra of RV. 1.92.8 Uṣas is requested to donate the wealth upon the worshippers which brings glory, bravery, servants, and horses in large number to them⁴. Similarly in RV. 7.75.8 people approach Uṣas for the wealth which brings cows, horses, sons, gems, and food grains⁵. It is to be said that the things were very dear to the Vedic people or closely associated with their day-to-day life were recognized as wealth. Among wealth, cattle were their favourite property. It was considered as wealth because of its utility for yielding milk and drawing loads from one place to another. Similarly, sons and grandsons were regarded as precious wealth because they were considered as extenders of family. Metals also had their significance in the form of coins as well as ornaments. Likewise, foodgrains were too considered as wealth because of their necessity for keeping people alive. By following these things, we can say the concept of Economy or wealth was broad but the exchange was different. The question is how the Vedic people get this wealth and how they exchange these items for their work. So, there are so many sources for exchanging the wealth, For example agriculture, cattle-rearing, dakṣiṇā and donation, fine arts, cottage industries, taxes etc. This is clear that with these sources and principles of income and expenditure the Vedic economy and national income was growing.

Livelihood of the Śūdras

The members of the fourth varṇa perhaps served the people of other higher varṇas as they were born from the feet of the creator. Sometimes, the Śūdras also helped in the religious rites. For example, it is laid down the sacrificer may bring fire from the house of a Śūdra⁶. It appears that the śūdras used to get something (i.e. wealth) as a reward for their services. As they were dependant of the other varṇas so they had no expenditure and they could save whatever money the masters gave them whenever they were pleased with their work. Besides, they were perhaps, engaged in other works also from which they could earn a lot to become rich. It is quite possible that the men of four strata and other low classes followed these occupations to earn their meals.

Livestock-Breeding

Livestock-breeding was an important occupation of the sutra period. The people kept big herds of cows, horses, goats, and sheep. Cattles were driven out to pastures in the morning and driven back to their enclosures in the evening. According to the Kātyāyana, a lack of cows were given away as sacrificial fees at the Rājasūya sacrifice⁷. It further adds that the elephants were reared mostly in the eastern part of India; horses in the western part and mules in northern part of India⁸. Cows, bull, oxen etc. were often given in dakṣiṇā which suggest that they were reared by the people in ancient times. The cattle wealth our country has an intimate bearing on its agricultural development, health, and economic prosperity of the people. The welfare of our people and the progress of our agriculture are

bound up with the welfare of our cattle. Bullocks are the means of transport everywhere in our villages and their power is available for various agricultural operations.

Fine arts

The practice of fine arts was a regular feature of Vedic cultural life. A man of culture enjoyed a high status in the society. Poetry-composition, music, dance, drama, painting, sculpture and architecture etc. naturally enjoyed the place of honour in the Vedic period. It is not sufficient to know only the names of the Vedic fine arts but more important is to have information about each of these different arts and their distinctive qualities. Besides, it is the most important fact to know that these fine arts were also accepted as the source of individual income by the Aryans. Here are some details of fine arts which were practised in sacrificial field.

Poetry and Music

The contents of Vedas show the poetic talent of the Aryans. RV. is entirely metrical and about fifteen metres have been used. There are two types of religious poetry in the RV. the superior level religious poetry consists praises of gods and usually accompanying the sacrifices made to them. And the lower-level religious poetry comprises spells or charms directed against hostile powers. We could trace in the RV. the origin of Hindu lyric, dramatic and epic poetry. The whole RV collection is lyric. Music consists two aspects, one individual communion and the other public performances. RV. and SV. are the oldest records of music of the

Aryans. The hymns used in the Soma sacrifice were certainly chanted by the priests. It is to be included that the people who chanted the hymns at the different ceremonies were supposed to get some wealth in return as their remuneration. Mantras from the SV. were often chanted by the rtviks at the time of sacrifice. It is to be said that although the rtviks recited these mantras for the fulfilment of religious purposes and for the welfare of the yajamana yet they were supposed to get some reward for their labour from the latter. Further, it is to be added that besides other purposes of music (kala), it was also accepted as an individual source of income in the Vedic society as today.

Cottage industries

Creativeness is the product of the human mind and industry develops on creativeness. This creativeness of mind made Aryans to invent several cottage industries like spinning and weaving, metals and metallurgy, leather, wood-work, pottery, plaiting etc. These cottage industries were recognised as the individual source of income in the Vedic period. Different commodities were produced and sent to the market so that people could get them easily or directly used in sacrificial field.

Textile industry

Textile industry was highly developed in the Vedic period and was recognised as an important source of income. People used to weave cloth for their and others use. It is evident from the references scattered throughout the Vedic Texts that people were very familiar with the techniques of spinning and weaving. Several technical terms concerning spinning and weaving have been referred to. Usually, the word tantu is mentioned for thread (warp)⁹. The word 'otu' for 'wool' corresponding to the word tantu (warp) frequently occurs in the Vedic Samhitas¹⁰. The weaving shuttle was called tasara¹¹ and the weaver was known by the name vāya¹².

There are several varieties of cloth which were manufactured by the Aryans. It is true that in some cases we are not sure about the materials from which the cloth was woven. Pāṇḍva was worn by the kings at the sacrifices¹³. Tāryya is an

other name for cloth referred to in the Vedic Texts¹⁴. The commentators suggest it to be a linen garment or one thrice soaked in ghee or one made of the tṛpa plant. Generally, women were doing this weaving works. It is evident that women had played an important role in the Vedic economy as today. And this kind of information says that by doing this work one kind of people was growing their economy. It is also related indirectly with the rituals, as in the sacrificial field they need various types of cloths and cloths were also been given as a Dakṣiṇā and donation in yajna.

Metals and Metallurgy

From very early period Aryans were familiar with metals and their uses. Many people adopted metal-work as their source of livelihood. Generally, five to six metals were known to the people of Vedic times as is clear from the references scattered throughout the Vedic literature¹⁵.

- (i) Hiranya, Suvāna, Harita - Gold.
- (ii) Ayas, yama, Karsnayasa - Iron or copper or bronze.
- (iii) Rajata - Silver.
- (iv) Lohā - Copper.
- (v) Śisā - Lead
- (vi) Trapu - Tin.

Here it has been said that the sacrificer enriches himself in these metals by performing sacrifice.

(1) Hiranya (gold) — Among the metals, hiraṇya (gold) is frequently referred to in the Vedic texts¹⁶. This shows that Aryans considered gold very valuable. It was obtained from river-beds and that is why sindhu is spoken of by the poets as rich in gold¹⁷. Different types of ornaments were made of gold. Gold was considered as the most highly esteemed gift and was given in the Dakṣiṇā to the priests¹⁸. Gold was also recognised as a medium of exchange. The words aṣṭāprūḍa and śatamāna, denoting units of exchange, are frequently mentioned in the Vedic Texts¹⁹. It is to be said that by analysing all the relevant references of gold in the vedic Texts we automatically arrive at an understanding of the metallurgical processes used to obtain gold. It is evident that the people of that time acquired the gold from the beds of the rivers. It appears that they then washed it with pure water and probably with the fine powder. After that, it was brought to the goldsmith's pot to be melted, then made into various articles of the people's use. By that process a big amount of people was involved, and they are growing their economy.

(2) Ayas — The metal ayas is often referred to in the Vedic texts next in importance to gold. It is clear from the references that the word 'ayas' generally denotes metal but when we examine of its different colours described in the Vedic texts, we find some differences in its exact form and it is difficult to decide the real form of metal at some places as in the rv.328 Here ayas suggests more its meaning bronze rather than iron. Ayas is itemised under two separate categories i.e. syama (iron) and lohita (copper or bronze). The word ayas definitely denotes iron²⁰. It is described that ayas 'iron' was fixed at the top of an arrow²¹. Ayas was also used for various purposes, like abhri²² (spade), dātra²³ (sickle), phāla²⁴ (ploughshare) etc. Besides, the smith also made equipment for protecting warriors in the battle, such as armour, helmet etc. So, according to the uses the smith was economically string by the profession.

(3) Rajata (silver) — Rajata was considered the third metal in the Vedic age. Generally, the term ayas denotes silver²⁵. It was used for making ornaments

(rukma)²⁶, dishes (pātra)²⁷ and coins (niṣka). As far as its colour is concerned it is referred to as whitish²⁸. It is to be said that we do not find frequent mention of rajata especially in the Samhitas and it seems that silver might have rarely been used in the remotest past and was not so favoured as gold by the Aryans.

Apart from these three metals (hiranya, ayas and rajata), trapu (tin)²⁹ and sīsā (lead)³⁰ were also known to the Vedic Aryans. People were also familiar with the use of maṇi³¹. As all of these are used in daily life and in the sacrificial field smiths, raw product supplier and the middleman were economically developed.

Wood-work

Wood-work was largely developed as an industry in the vedic age. It was accepted as the most important source of income. Aryans were predominantly agriculturists and they needed implements to cultivate the land and vehicles for carrying their crops from the fields. It is clear from the references scattered throughout the Vedic texts that people were much interested in making chariots. The industry of chariot-making became so important that chariotmakers were considered to form a separate class and distinguished from carpenters. The services of a carpenter were especially needed when a 'yūpa' (sacrificial post) was to be made for the sacrifice. Besides, a large number of chariots were also needed in a sacrifice such as in the vajapeya³². A wheel with seventeen spokes was also a ritual need there and Brahmā had to be seated on the top of the tall post or on the pole of the chariot and then the wheel of seventeen spokes was to be moved round³³. It is to be said that the proficiency of a carpenter was an integral part of a sacrifice.

Besides, the houses were also made of wood. AV. 9.3.1 throws light on the art of building houses. A full hymn of RV. VII. 54 deals with the art of house-building. Wood craft was also indispensable for agricultural and transportation purposes along with chariot-making. Boats and ships made of wood are frequently mentioned in the Vedic literature and the art of ship-building was so common to the people that the sacrificial rite was compared to ship-building. House-hold and sacrificial utensils such as, dhruvā, juhū, sruva (ladles)³⁴, udaca (bucket)³⁵, camasam (bowl)³⁶ etc. were also made of wood. In YV. a list of utensils required in performing a sacrifice is also given as - sruk (ladle)³⁷, vāyavya (spoon)³⁸, droṇa-kalāśa³⁹ etc.

Pottery

References to pottery indicate that this art was also well known to the Aryans. They used to manufacture pots for their domestic use as well as for sacrificial purposes. Moreover, pottery was recognised as a source of income. Kalasa and Kumbha were jars and pots respectively and made of clay or some metal⁴⁰. These were usually needed for every household. The word kulāla and mṛtpaca denoting a potter. Soma juice was also stored in these vessels⁴¹. The potters were called on and especially instructed by the king to manufacture vessels of big as well as small size for the performance of the Aśvamedha sacrifice.

Transport and Communication

Transport was a very important part of the national economy because it helped in disposing off the products of the trade to their proper destinations. Chariots and carts drawn by oxen and horses were most important means of Communication⁴². Chariot was the most popular vehicle of those days. Usually two animals were yoked, but there are references that sometimes the chariot was drawn by four or five horses⁴³. Generally, a cart or a chariot had two wheels, but Baudhāyana speaks of a cart with four wheels⁴⁴. A cart drawn by bullocks was used for the pur-

pose of carrying load from one place to another. A big cart was used for carrying heavy loads. Elephants, camels, horses, and asses were used for riding⁴⁵. Boats were generally used to cross the rivers⁴⁶.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the Vedic conception of wealth and livelihood reflects a well-structured and dynamic economic system deeply rooted in natural resources, social organization, and religious practices. Wealth was not confined to material accumulation but included cattle, food, metals, and progeny, all of which were essential for sustaining life and ensuring social continuity. The idea of “natural social wealth” underscores the collective approach of the Vedic people towards resource utilization and management. The economic framework of the Vedic period was marked by diversification and specialization. Occupations such as livestock-breeding, agriculture, textile production, metallurgy, pottery, and woodwork contributed significantly to economic growth and stability. These industries not only fulfilled everyday needs but also supported the elaborate ritualistic practices that characterized Vedic culture.

The integration of economy with religion is one of the most distinctive features of this period. Sacrifices and rituals served as mechanisms for the redistribution of wealth, ensuring that different sections of society, including priests, artisans, and laborers, were compensated for their contributions. The system of dakṣiṇā further reinforced economic exchange and social cohesion. Moreover, the participation of Śūdras and other lower strata in various economic activities demonstrates that the Vedic economy was inclusive to a certain extent, relying on the contributions of all sections of society. Despite their subordinate social position, their economic role was indispensable. Overall, the study reveals that the Vedic economy was not primitive or unorganized, but rather a complex and evolving system characterized by interdependence, resource management, and cultural integration. It laid the foundational principles for later economic developments in ancient India and continues to provide valuable insights into the relationship between economy, society, and religion in early human civilization.

Endnotes

1. पशवो वै रयिः। - TS. 1.5.7.2
2. प्रजननं परमं वदन्ति। - Mahānā. Up. 12.1
3. अन्नं वाजः। - TS. 3.5.7.2, ŚB. 5.1.1.16
4. उषस्तमश्यां यशसं सुवीरं दासप्रवगं रयिमश्चबुध्यम्। सुदंससा श्रवसा या विभासि वाजप्रसूता सुभगे बृहन्तम्।
5. नू नो गोमद्वीरवद्धेहि रत्नमुषो अश्वावत्पुरुभोजो अस्मे। मा नो बर्हिः पुरुषता निदे कर्युयं पात स्वस्तिभिः सदा नः ॥
6. Āp.Ś.S. 5.11-18
7. Kāt. Ś.S. 15.4.43
8. Kāt. Ś.S. 15.4.43
9. RV. 6.9.2-3; 10.134.5; AV. 14.2.51
10. RV. 6.9.2; AV. 14.2.51
11. RV. 10.130.2
12. RV. 10.26.6
13. SB. 5.3.5.21
14. SB. 5.3.5.20; AV. 18.4.31
15. YV. 18.13
16. RV. 1.43.5; 3.34.9; 4.10.6
17. RV. 10.75.8; 8.26.18
18. RV. 6.47.23
19. TS. 3.4.1.4; SB. 5.5.5.16; 12.7.2.13

20. AV. 5.28.1
21. RV. 6.75.15
22. AV. 4.7.5-6
23. RV. 8.78.10
24. RV. 4.57.3
25. SB. 12.4.4.7
26. SB. 12.8.3.11
27. TB. 2.2.9.7
28. RV. 8.25.22
29. AV. 11.3.8
30. AV. 1.16.2
31. RV. 1.33.8
32. हस्तिवह्यकमहानसानाम् KSS. 14.2.31
33. देवस्याह मिति ब्रह्मा रथचक्रमारोहत्युत्करे नाभिमात्रे स्थाणौ स्थितम् KSS. 14.3.12
34. AV. 18.4.5-6
35. AV. 4.15.16
36. RV. 4.35.2
37. YV. 8.21
38. YV. 8.21
39. YV. 8.21
40. RV. 1.117.12; RV. 1.191.14
41. RV. 3.32.15
42. Kāt.22.10.31
43. Ap.Ś.S. 14.3.11; 18.9.10-14
44. Bau.Ś.S. 17.5.4
45. Bau.Ś.S. 11.6
46. Bau.Ś.S. 18.40

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